

Spring Distribution, Associated Environment and Strategies for Sustainable Development in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province, Pakistan

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ABSTRACT

Rapid growth in urbanization coupled with climate change has significantly increased the water demand for domestic, agricultural, and industrial use in the Indus basin. Although spring resource is essential for the sustenance of a large number of mountain communities in the region, it has not been extensively studied yet. The current study is aimed at exploring spring resource potential in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan, for improving water security in the province. The findings of the study revealed a total of 4386 springs in the KPK, having a density of about 0.04 springs/km². The highest concentration of springs was identified in the low mountains, i.e., 31.3%, followed by Siwaliks, i.e., 22.6%. The rainfall zone >1250 mm exhibited the maximum concentration of springs (1337), followed by 1000–1250 mm zone (958), where spring densities were found to be 0.12 sp/km² and 0.07 sp/km², respectively. Maximum of about 40.5% springs were identified in the 0.4–0.6 NDVI class, followed by 27.3% in the 0.2–0.4 class. The spring density indicated an exponential increase with the rainfall data pointing towards a significant contribution of moisture conditions in sustaining the spring resource. The spring water may be conserved through developing storage tanks or ponds for household and irrigation use especially during lean periods. The study underscores the need for targeted interventions in spring-shed management, infrastructure development, and governance system to ensure spring water security in the region. Moreover, it is necessary to comprehend the hydrogeology of the area, which controls the spring flows and study impacts of ecology, socioeconomics and developmental activities on the spring ecosystem in future.

INTRODUCTION.

Many mountain communities worldwide rely on spring water resource to meet their water needs for drinking, livestock, and small-scale irrigation (Chinnasamy and Prathapar 2016; Chapagain et al., 2019; Gosavi et al. 2021). Springs are naturally occurring groundwater outflows, which form a valuable source of freshwater for millions of mountain communities and natural ecosystems in the Hindu Kush-Himalayan region (ICIMOD 2021; Pant et al. 2024; Ashraf et al. 2025). They are formed when groundwater seeps to the surface from the faults, fractures of some rock formations and underground aquifers (Kresic, 2010). Springs are vital for promoting freshwater ecosystem and biodiversity in the mountain ecologies, besides meeting the communities' cultural, social and water needs in the region (Tambe et al. 2012). In the northern mountainous region of Pakistan, perennial springs contribute flows to streams, rivers, lakes, and wetland ecosystems. They are dynamic and diverse due to a variety of geological, hydrological, and environmental factors (Pitts and Alfaro 2001; Soulios 2017). The groundwater use has increased rapidly owing to growth in urbanization, agricultural activities, and extreme drought conditions in the Indus basin (Qureshi 2011; Laghari et al. 2012; Sadaf et al. 2019). Springs are regarded as a safe domestic and drinking source by the local communities. Pant et al. (2024) evaluated springs and transdisciplinary water resource management in the Himalayan region to help develop an ethnographic review of the springs for the last 30 years. Despite their vital importance, spring management and conservation have received comparatively little attention. Effective protection of the spring ecosystems and water resource management needs basic geographic data and field information for sustainable development (Stevens et al. 2021).

The sustainable development of spring resources has not been given enough priority in policies and procedures (Ashraf et al. 2025). Although several studies are found on the Himalayan spring resources (Negi and Joshi 2004; Poudel and Duex 2017; Lamichhane et al. 2020), but the distribution of springs and how they respond to environmental risks have not been studied in the Hindu Kush region. Few studies in this region were focused on investigating the water quality of the selected springs for drinking purposes (Ahmed et al. 2017; Ali et al. 2019; Nawab et al. 2023; Ullah et al. 2023). The majority of springs are still not well surveyed, and little is known about their conservation status despite the vital water requirements (Cantonati et al. 2020). It is essential to provide basic geographic information about the springs to the water management and conservation organizations to effectively manage spring ecosystems. There is a need to assess the potential of spring resources and manage them efficiently for sustainable agriculture and livelihoods in the country. It is

hypothesized that there exist prospects of spring resources in this region that can be sustained through proper management for future livelihood improvement in this region.

The present study is aimed at exploring spring resource potential in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) province of Pakistan using geospatial techniques and ground information. The study would provide a base for understanding the spring dynamics, preparing a detail inventory and developing appropriate guidelines for effective spring water management in the region.

Geographical setup

The KPK province stretches over an area of about 101,741 km² (population 40.8 million) within elevation ranging from less 200 m to more than 7400 m, in the northwest of Pakistan. The northern glaciated region experiences pleasant summers, extremely cold and snowy winters, while the southern hills and plains experience hotter summers and fairly less severe winters. The annual precipitation ranges from less than 300 mm in the southwest to more than 1500 mm in the northeast mountains. The province has a total of 1.88 million ha of cultivated area (8.5% of the country's total cultivated area), and about half of the cultivable land depends on rainfed agriculture (Shah et al. 2021). The summer rains are usually received during monsoon season from June to September, whereas winter rainfall occurs from westerly during November to February. Livestock holds the central position in the livelihood of farming communities in major mountain areas. Major agricultural systems are irrigated agriculture and rainfed and dryland agriculture. The main crops grown are wheat, maize, rice, pulses and variety of vegetables and fruits. The main sources of water in the province are the Indus River and its tributaries, groundwater, and springs. At places, the local communities are responsible for taking care of, managing, and distributing the spring water. To supply spring water to fields and villages, many areas rely on small infrastructure and gravity-fed channels (Ashraf and Ahmad 2021).

Geology and hydrogeology

The geology is characterized by sedimentary rocks surrounded by metamorphic and igneous rocks characterized by complex setup, intense folding and faulting (Kadri 1995). In the northeastern part, the geology consists of rock formations ranging in age from Precambrian to Quaternary and unconsolidated material (Ahsan and Chaudhry 2008; Qamar et al. 2021). The fractured igneous rocks, i.e., granites and gneisses, may have some yield potential appeared in the form of fracture springs. Permian rocks consist of mostly shale, limestone, chert, and sandstone, whereas alluvium deposits are partially present in the intermountain valleys (Kazmi and Jan 1997). Various types of springs exist in the area, e.g., artesian springs, fracture springs, gravity springs or depression springs, contact springs, and thermal springs (Stevens et al.

2021). Contact springs, or seepage springs, occur in depressions or valley bottoms where groundwater seeps out slowly to the ground surface from contacts of relatively permeable rocks overlying impermeable or low-permeable rock layers. The soils in the valleys are mostly deep and developed from piedmont alluvium and loess deposits (Khan et al. 2011). Thermal springs release warm water even during severe cold winters (e.g., Garam Chashma in the Chitral district). Based on flow characteristics, there are perennial springs that flow year round, and intermittent springs that run during wet seasons only. The main recharge sources include winter snow, rainfall and stream/river flows. Spring recharge is affected by human activities, e.g. unplanned urban development, deforestation, and over-extraction, besides climate change, while its discharge depends on the aquifer water pressure, recharge characteristics and size of the springshed (Li et al. 2017; Virk et al. 2020).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Data used

The baseline data of topography, administrative units, springs, climate, soils and crops was gathered from different source departments, including the Survey of Pakistan (SoP), Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD), Soil survey and agriculture departments of the province. The spring data was based on the Global positioning surveys conducted by SoP across different districts of the province. The remote sensing data of Copernicus Global Land Cover product (2020) and the European space agency (ESA) (2021) were used to assess extent of major land use/land cover (LULC) classes in the study area. The NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) eight-day seamless product 250 m (2020) available at website <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/> was downloaded to analyze vegetative and non-vegetative areas. Similarly, the SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) DEM 90 m available at the NASA website (www.jpl.nasa.gov/) was acquired for topographic (elevation, slope) analysis. The ground data and information of irrigation sources, land use, socioeconomics and community perceptions were gathered through field observations, questionnaire and focal group discussion from selected sites of the study area. Owing to geographical and accessibility limitations, it was difficult to get spring discharges; therefore, an analog approach based on approximations from earlier research carried out around this region was chosen. For example, the spring discharge typically ranged within 0.01 to 10 liters per second in the Himalayan region (Pandit et al. 2024).

Spatial data preparation

The thematic data layers were developed using Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM) coordinate system for integration and analysis in ArcGIS software. Precipitation, geomorphology, soil properties, and land use-land cover (LULC) have a significant impact on springs (Fiorillo, 2009; Negi and Joshi, 2004). The physiographic zones were developed based on elevation zoning (Hubert (1995) and others), which include lowlands (0-300 m) over 9.6%, plateau/hilly area (300-700 m) 20.8%, siwaliks (700-1200 m) 17.8%, lower mountains (1200-2000 m) 17.4%, middle mountains (2000-3000 m) 12.1%, and high mountains (>3000 m) over 22.3% of the province area.

The slope classes were defined following Ashraf and Ahmad (2024) to assess influence on the spring distribution, i.e., the $<5^\circ$ class (flat to gentle slope), 5° – 15° (gentle to moderate slope), 15° – 30° (moderate to steep slope), 30° – 45° (steep slope) and $>45^\circ$ class (very steep slope). The relationship of spring distribution was studied with various associated bio-physical factors and agro-ecologies for impact assessment. The agro-ecological zones were delineated using base data of agro-climate, physiography, landforms/soils and land use of the study area. Agro-ecological zones provide relevant information on the existing status of the environment, which is important for prioritizing research in agriculture and natural resources (Fischer et al. 2006). The rainfall and reference evapotranspiration (Eto) data (calculated using temperature data) were used to form agro-climatic classes of the province (Roohi et al. 2002). A spring concentration index was defined for planning and decision making at district level in the study area (Table 2). Finally, spring management strategies were developed to help ensure equitable water distribution, addressing water storage and conveyance gaps, and safeguard water quality in the region.

Table 2. Index of spring concentration classes in the study area.

S. No.	Springs	Concentration
1	>300	High
2	200–300	Fair
3	100–200	Moderate
4	50–100	Medium
5	<50	Low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Spatial analysis of springs

The study findings revealed a total of 4386 springs in the KPK province with density of over 0.04 springs/km². The spring concentration varies in different districts of the province depending on the biophysical and climatic conditions. It was observed maximum in the Mansehra and Abbottabad districts (Figure 1), likely because of receiving higher monsoon rains during summers and snow in winters. The spring concentration was observed fair in the lower Chitral, upper Dir, Kurram, Buner, Haripur, and South Waziristan districts, whereas it was moderate in the north Chitral, Swat, Kohistan, Lower Dir, Shangla, Batagram, Kohat and some other districts. The springs here are generally perennial and mainly recharged through snow precipitation that occurred in the uplands. In Kohat, the spring known as ‘*Chashma Mir Habib*’ is popular for recreation during the summer season besides irrigation, and another smaller one called ‘*Mohammad Ali Chashma*’ is for irrigation purposes. The spring concentration was medium in the Hangu, Orakzai, Bajaur, Mohmand, Malakand, Kolai-Palas and Torghar, districts. On the other hand, low concentration of springs was observed in some central and southern districts including Swabi, Mardan, Nowshera and Tank, due to having less favorable topography and climatic conditions.

Figure 1. Spring concentration in different districts of the study area.

A maximum of about 31.3% of springs were identified over low mountains (density about 0.08 sp/km²) followed by 22.6% over siwaliks (density over 0.05 sp/km²) (Figure 2, Table 3). The spring concentration was observed within the 10-20% range in the high mountains, middle mountains, and plateau, exhibiting densities between 0.02 and 0.06 sp/km². The spring types vary with geology and hydrology of the area (Pitts and Alfaro 2001). High concentration of springs, i.e., about 40.1%, was observed over 15°–30° slope class, 33.3% over 5°–15° slope and 16.3% over <5° slope class. Less than 500 springs were observed over >30° slope class in the province. The rainfall zone >1250 mm exhibited the maximum number of springs (1337), followed by the 1000–1250 mm zone (958), where spring densities were found to be 0.12 sp/km² and 0.07 sp/km², respectively (Table 3 and Figure 2). The least density of springs, i.e., about 0.02 sp/km², was observed in the <500 mm rainfall zone, exhibiting serious implications of low rainfall condition on the groundwater system.

Table 3. Spring distribution in different bio-physical conditions in the KPK province.

Region	Coverage		Springs		Density (sp/km ²)
	Km ²	%	Number	%	
Lowlands	9766	9.6	13	0.3	0.00
Plateau	21171	20.8	488	11.1	0.02
Siwaliks	18109	17.8	992	22.6	0.05
Low mountains	17657	17.4	1373	31.3	0.08
Middle mountains	12308	12.1	779	17.8	0.06
High mountains	22730	22.3	741	16.9	0.03
Slope					
<5°	37125	36.5	714	16.3	0.02
5°–15°	25143	24.7	1462	33.3	0.06
15°–30°	27002	26.5	1760	40.1	0.07
30°–45°	10589	10.4	412	9.4	0.04
>45°	1881	1.8	38	0.9	0.02
Rainfall (mm)					
<500	39029	38.4	828	18.9	0.02
500–750	29600	29.1	874	19.9	0.03
750–1000	7942	7.8	389	8.9	0.05
1000–1250	14294	14.0	958	21.8	0.07
>1250	10875	10.7	1337	30.5	0.12

NDVI					
≤ 0	6879	6.8	13	0.3	0.00
0–0.2	24498	24.1	776	17.7	0.03
0.2–0.4	35621	35.0	1196	27.3	0.03
0.4–0.6	30056	29.5	1778	40.5	0.06
>0.6	4687	4.6	623	14.2	0.13
LULC					
Forest	19637	19.3	1505	34.3	0.08
Rangeland	50073	49.2	1908	43.5	0.04
Cropland	13270	13.0	597	13.6	0.04
Others	18761	18.4	376	8.6	0.02
Total	101741	100.0	4386	100.0	0.04

Figure 2. Springs in various bio-physical regions of the study are

The spring density indicated an exponential increase with annual rainfall of the area (Figure 3), pointing towards a significant role of rainfall in sustaining spring resource in the area. Such influence of rainfall was also studied by various researchers for different parts of the Hindu Kush-Himalayan region (e.g. Negi and Joshi 2004; Chang et al. 2021; Ashraf and Ali 2025). About 14.2% springs were observed in the >0.6 NDVI class representing high-density

vegetation, with the highest spring density of about 0.13 sp/km². The higher NDVI indicates wet conditions as result of favorable subsurface moisture availability in a region (Yun-Hao et al. 2003). The spring density appears to exhibit an exponential increase with the NDVI of the area (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Relationship of spring density with different bio-physical factors.

About 34.3% of springs were identified in the forest class that exhibited a high spring density of about 0.08 sp/km² (Table 4). The soil capacity to absorb and hold water is generally increased due to presence of extensive forest cover. The degradation of forests and removal of vegetation cover usually slow down the infiltration process in soils, consequently affecting the recharge of groundwater and springs. According to spring analysis by agro-ecology, the concentration of springs was found to be highest in the sub-humid valleys (SHV) zone (Table 4 and Figure 4), where snow and rain precipitation forms a major source of spring recharge.

Some dense patches of forest cover exist over gentle to steep mountain slopes here, which also favor recharge process of the springs. About 15% springs were observed in the semi-arid valleys (SAV), where occasional rainfall and surface runoff form the main sources of spring recharge. The northern dry mountains (NDM) zone contains about 6% springs, which are typically recharged by the snow and glacial meltwater. The high-altitude glaciers here generally support the traditional gravity-flow irrigation system for sustaining agriculture and livelihoods downstream (Ashraf and Ahmad 2021). Maximum spring density (about 0.15 sp/km²) was observed in the high rainfall zone (HRZ) where mean annual precipitation generally exceeds 1400 mm and supports creation and sustainability of the springs. Moreover, extensive patches of coniferous forest and herbaceous vegetation favor groundwater and spring

recharge due to prevalent wet conditions here. The Suleiman mountains (SM) and piedmont plain (PP) zones contain about 5.9% and 2.8% springs (Table 4), which provide water supplies for small-scale irrigation and domestic use at places. The valley plain (VP) contains at least about 1.9% springs (Figure 4), because of retaining flat to gentle topography and absence of suitable geology for the spring formation.

Figure 4. Spring distribution in different agro-ecological zones of KPK province.

Table 4. Summary of spring concentration in various agro-ecological zones.

Zone	Coverage%	Elevation (m)	Rainfall (mm)	Springs		Density (sp/km ²)
				Number	%	
NDM	13.0	4107	465	261	6.0	0.02
SHV	35.9	2223	982	2489	56.7	0.07
HRZ	3.3	1295	1420	511	11.7	0.15
SAV	20.5	1258	521	659	15.0	0.03
P	6.2	395	721	82	1.9	0.01
M	6.7	914	355	260	5.9	0.04
P	14.3	316	415	124	2.8	0.01
total	100.0	1501	697	4386	100.0	0.04

Perception of Spring Dependent Community

Hazara division (HD) containing majority of over 1586 springs in the northwestern part of the KPK (Figure 5) was selected for detail analyze of the spring dependent communities. Major area of the HD consists of forest cover and rangeland dominated over 88% of the area. Annual rainfall greater than 1100 mm prevails in most of the area, which tends to exceed 1500 mm towards southeast (Figure 6). The high and middle mountains are dominant over 58% of the

area. Over 74.7% of the area comprises mountain-valley system landform, which consists of fair to good soil cover and 11.3% snow and glacial deposits (Figure 6). The springs serve as the primary source of clean water for over 0.12 million households in this division (Table 5). The findings of the Hi-Aware project study on springshed management were used to estimate the spring water use per household. Overall, 13% of the population of HD appears to depend on the spring resource. Maximum of about 35.4% springs were observed in the Mansehra district (density about 0.14 sp/km²) and 20.9% in the Abbottabad district (density about 0.17 sp/km²) (Figure 5). In the former district, springs support around 49,960 households (nearly 15.3% of the district population), while in the latter, they serve around 26,480 households (about 11% of the district population). There exist 227 springs in the Haripur district, which serve over 18,160 households (about 9.4% of the district population).

Figure 5 Spring distribution in Hazara division.

In the Kolai-Palas district, 167 springs were identified, which serve about 13360 households with over 32.9% of the district population—representing high dependency on the spring water. Similarly, in Batagram district (area about 497 km²), about 8.7% of the springs serve around 11,040 households with around 21.4% of the district population—representing a significant dependency on the springs. In fact, the maximum spring density, i.e., about 0.28 sp/km² points toward favorable recharge conditions for spring formation in this district. Upper Kohistan district containing 4.5% of the springs supports 5680 households (about 7.9% of the district population), while lower Kohistan containing a least of about 1.8% of the springs serves around 2240 households (about 4.2% of the district population) (Table 5). The low-

dependency of the people on spring water in these districts points toward presence of alternate water sources, such as river and stream flows for irrigation and domestic use.

Figure 6. Extent of land use, rainfall, physiography and landform classes in the Hazara division.

Table 5. Summary of spring dependent households (HH) and percentage of district population (DP) in Hazara division.

District	Area (km ²)	Springs*	Springs %	Population	HH size	Spring Dependent Households (**80HH/Sp)	Spring dependent Population (% of DP)
Upper Kohistan	5440	71	4.5	422947	.9	5680	7.9
Lower Kohistan	642	28	1.8	340017	.4	2240	4.2
Kolai-Palas	1410	167	10.5	280162	.9	13360	32.9
Mansehra	4125	562	35.4	1797177	.1	44960	15.3
Batagram	497	138	8.7	335984	.5	11040	21.4
Torghar	454	62	3.9	200445	.8	4960	16.8
Abbottabad	1967	331	20.9	1419072	.9	26480	11.0
Haripur	1725	227	14.3	1174783	.1	18160	9.4
Total/Avg.	16260	1586	100.0	5970587	.3	126880	13.2

Data source: *Survey of Pakistan and Population census of Pakistan 2023**Hi-Aware Project study

During field survey conducted in the Galiyat village – Budhar (73°23'04"E, 34°03'09"N, Elevation 2022 m) in Tehsil & District Abbottabad (Figure 7), focal group discussions and consultation were held with the local community to gather information on water related issues, environmental risks and spring water use in the area. According to the information shared by the community, the perennial springs form a major source of freshwater for drinking and household use in the village. Water distribution practices vary by location in the area. For example, the communities residing downhill from springs rely on gravity flow to channel water from the storage tanks, whereas households located at higher elevations have to depend on electric motor systems to pump water upwards. According to the respondents, though springs are running throughout the year in their village, but few springs have dried up in their neighboring region over time. The quality of water from their spring has not changed significantly and continues to be used for drinking and domestic purposes. The quantity of spring water is insufficient to meet the agricultural requirements, consequently the agriculture practices, once the main livelihood of the community, has declined sharply. According to the locals, the limited availability of water, coupled with rapid population growth and lifestyle changes, has intensified domestic demand while reducing opportunities for agricultural production.

Figure 7 A spring-dependent Galiyat village in Abbottabad district (Surveyed in 2023).

According to the villagers, the 2005 earthquake disrupted many springs across the Galiyat region, causing some to dry completely, others to change their path, and some to produce contaminated water intermittently. In addition, shifts in rainfall and snowfall patterns have been observed. In the past, snowfall mostly occurred within 4–15 inches during December to March, but in recent years, it has declined to one or two events per season, rarely exceeding 2–3 inches. Similarly, rainfall previously occurred during the summer (July–August) and spring (March–April) seasons, now become erratic and intense in the recent years. The climatic variability and shift have adversely affected spring recharge and water availability. According to the farmers in the nearby Soan basin, rainfall pattern has changed, and shallow groundwater sources are becoming less available (Ahmad et al., 2023). Approximately 70–80 households (around 350–400 individuals) depend on this spring as their primary source of drinking and domestic water. The village currently relies on a very small and outdated storage tank (4x4x5 ft) connected to a main distribution pipeline. This infrastructure is insufficient to meet community needs, and the pipeline system suffers frequent leakages due to its old and deteriorated condition. The main line connects to smaller household distribution lines, but the limited water volume results in highly uneven distribution, with many households not receiving enough to meet daily requirements. While no formal water management committee exists at present, participants agreed that such a body should be established on a demand basis. According to the locals, though agriculture is no longer the dominant livelihood here, their lands remain suitable for crops such as potatoes, vegetables (including off-season vegetables),

and fruits like apple, apricot, peach. Revitalizing spring water systems could therefore support diversified agriculture and improved food security.

Sustainable spring management

The water resources in the mountainous region are under increasing pressure owing to unplanned urban development, deforestation and climate change (Laghari et al. 2012). The changes in land use particularly deforestation, rangeland degradation, and urban expansion pose significant risks to the sustainability of spring resource in terms of quantity and quality. In most cases, the spring sources are open and exposed to degraded environment (Figure 8) that can create water quality risks and health problems for local people. Effective management of this water resource is required to boost production, food security, and socioeconomic advancement in the region. According to Pant et al. (2024), sustainable management of water resources can be ensured through advancing a transdisciplinary, community-centric approach.

Figure 8 Springs form an important water source for local communities.

There is a serious lack of knowledge about how to recover dried or drying up springs and how to collect and store spring water. The current infrastructure is further weakened by the lack of regulations governing the supply of drinking water to grazing animals. Unless appropriately managed, sanitation and livestock operations in catchments can put pressure on springs, ponds, and small storage facilities (Abbas et al. 2021). This competition for access to limited water

sources often sparks conflicts and disputes among community members. Farm ponds and storage tanks can help retain the spring water for use in subsequent dry spells. Rooftop rainwater harvesting (RWH) has potential to provide tens to hundreds of cubic meters per household each year and lessen dependency on spring water during the dry months (Abbas et al. 2021). Investment is required for spring protection and maintenance, e.g. fencing the recharge areas, establishing spring protection box and storage tank, and preparing community operation guidelines to preserve yield and quality. Drying or improperly maintained springs that don't have enough systems for storage, transportation, or distribution result in losses of the limited available spring water (ICIMOD 2021). In order to ensure sustainable solutions for the well-being of the people in the face of water scarcity and climate shocks, scientific induced local knowledge initiatives are essential. The key barriers and opportunities were identified through field based assessment and coping measures were proposed to improve spring management (Table 6).

Table 6. Summary of key barriers/issues and intervention options for improving spring management.

Barriers/Issues	Intervention options
Changing rainfall and snowfall patterns	Establish mechanism for monitoring local climate and spring discharge for trend analysis
Water scarcity due to dried/drying springs or poor management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote groundwater recharge interventions (both structural & Biological measures) • Adopt ICIMOD 6-step methodology for spring revival, and rooftop RWH using efficient irrigation technologies especially for promoting orchards and kitchen gardening • Develop contingency plans and diversify water sources • Improve capacity and maintenance of water storage tanks as per scientific design, covered community storage tanks
Lack of proper conveyance systems leading to inefficient delivery	Design gravity-based conveyance systems; establish maintenance protocols
Water losses in piped	Replace old pipelines with HDPE leak-proof pipelines and

distribution system	connect sub-lines for household distribution
Knowledge gap on spring water use efficiency and water harvesting/storage methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community training on efficient water use and irrigation methods, and rainwater water harvesting techniques • Awareness campaigns on water conservation at household level (using smart taps and other water efficient appliances) • Water resource assessment under changing environment
Contamination of open sources by animal defecation, increasing health risks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct water quality testing and promote treatment practices (boiling, filtration) • Provide separate livestock drinking troughs supplied by secondary pipelines
Lack of formal water management committee to resolve management issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form Spring water user associations (WUAs)/Committees (WUCs) to ensure equitable distribution of water, resolve conflicts and promote water conservation practices • Create Technical Working Teams (TWTs) for monitoring and maintenance of the spring resource

There exists no mechanism of monitoring spring flows and water quality on regular basis and hardly any data on these aspects is available in the literature (Ahmad et al. 2023; Rana et al. 2025). An integrated spring governance framework and a specific institutional mechanism would be beneficial for maintaining spring inventory and protection. The sustainability of the springs demands its revival through springshed management which is crucial for water security of the mountain communities (Buono 2019; Gayen 2021). Some of practices in the field include small check dams and local recharge techniques to supplement shallow aquifers, and improvement in household sanitation to lower the risk of contamination. To go beyond perception data and allow adaptive management, set up baseline flow and quality monitoring for representative springs (Ahmad et al. 2023; Rana et al. 2025). A participatory approach may be ensured for managing spring resource and putting the required regulations into place. Provision of subsidies/finance would be helpful in initiating community-based spring management and protection projects, and efficient irrigation packages (Abbas et al. 2021).

CONCLUSION

The present study is aimed at exploring spring resource potential in the KPK province for improving water security in the region. A total of 4386 springs were identified in the KPK indicating a density of about 0.04 sp/km² in the province. The rainfall zone >1250 mm exhibited maximum number of springs (1337), followed by 1000–1250 mm zone (958), where spring densities were found to be 0.12 sp/km² and 0.07 sp/km², respectively. About 40.5% springs were identified in the 0.4–0.6 NDVI class and 27.3% in the 0.2–0.4 class. The spring density appears to exhibit an exponential increase with annual rainfall data of the area, pointing towards a high influence of moisture availability in nurturing the spring resource. The arid ecologies, like semi-arid valleys, piedmont plains, and the Suleiman

Mountains, necessitate adoption of appropriate interventions like rainwater harvesting, storages/farm ponds and water-smart technologies (drip, sprinkler, bubbler, etc.) for sustainable agriculture. Afforestation/reforestation needs to be promoted and check dams and storage ponds built at appropriate locations in the upstream of catchments to maintain recharge of the springs. It is necessary to increase awareness and build capacity of the local communities in contemporary water conservation practices and efficient water use to support water security in the area. Future research should be focused on understanding groundwater hydrology of the springs, and developing decision support tools, guidelines and effective governance system for sustainable management of the spring resource in the region.

DECLARATIONS

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